

PREPARING THE FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER TO IMPLEMENT INDIVIDUALLY DIFFERENTIATED LEARNING

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Abstract. *Systematic adherence to an individual and differentiated approach to students makes it possible to improve the quality of children's knowledge and the level of their skills. The use of tasks at different levels helps to maintain interest in studying academic subjects. But their use should in no way lead to the stratification of children's society according to their level of ability. With a differentiated approach to children, the level of knowledge acquisition significantly increases and certain positive successes in work are achieved.*

Keywords: *mathematics, primary education, differentiated tasks, theoretical justification, training, primary education.*

When organizing individual work, it is important to arouse students' interest in classes and the desire to eliminate gaps in knowledge, and for this it is necessary to instill in them confidence in their abilities; it is necessary to reveal to students the reasons for their lagging behind and indicate ways to eliminate the gaps; It is necessary to closely monitor students and note their slightest successes.

Since the formation of educational actions, the development of abilities, cognitive processes, and interest in learning in younger schoolchildren occurs in activities, the teacher must organize it, taking into account individual psychological characteristics. Differentiation is an organizational and methodological principle of teaching in primary school and creates conditions for individualization of the educational process. Let's consider the concepts of "differentiation of instruction," "differentiated instruction," "individualization," differentiated approach, and their relationship. The desire to learn is formed in the process of successfully working on the material, so it is important to organize individual assistance in such a way that the student constantly feels that he is moving forward; The volume and difficulty of tasks should be increased gradually. When working with children, I strive to manage their activities in such a way that everyone (necessarily everyone) feels the inspiring power of success.

Success at work is a primary condition for the development of a person's personality. This is inner comfort, a joyful mood when things are going well. for school, this is especially important. A child, if his efforts are not crowned with success, begins to lose faith in his abilities. Gradually, failures discourage learning: why, they say, nothing will work out anyway. You need to try to support a student who has failed, cheer him up, and be sure to praise him even for a small step forward.

As experience shows, often even minor progress inspires students and encourages them to work more intensely. the accessibility of the task strengthens the child's self-confidence, puts him in a situation of success, and maintains cognitive interest.

In the context of differentiated learning, homework is an organic continuation of class work and carries out a targeted function. Multi-level homework contributes to the development of self-

control, responsibility, hard work and other personal qualities, which in turn influence the formation of the student's gnostic (cognitive) qualities.

So, the development of differentiated tasks both in the classroom and at home is based on a systematic study of the difficulties that students experience in mastering the material, studying the gaps in their knowledge, an in-depth analysis of their current independent work, and a clear classification of errors. Deficiencies in the development of individual students must also be taken into account: unstable attention, slow pace of work, level of speech development, and others. The main thing in this work is systematic monitoring of students' educational activities and their health.

Pedagogy has always talked about the need for an individual approach to children, taking into account their inclinations and developmental characteristics. Most often, a teacher works in a class filled with children with different levels of preparedness and different abilities. Children learn material differently, have different attitudes to what needs to be learned, understood, absorbed, and remembered. Therefore, even the most methodologically perfect lesson will not necessarily be successful. We agree with the famous psychologist M. Djumaev that "the effect of training depends not only on its content and methods, but also on the individual characteristics of the students." The need for differentiated education is becoming more and more acute, since the school must give every child the opportunity to receive a general education minimum at the level of his abilities, capabilities and desires.

Pedagogy offers two ways to solve the problem of individualization:

- the first option requires the preparation of a special individual education program for each capable child, which is extremely difficult in the specific conditions of the school;
- the second option is universal equality in approach, when differentiating certain groups of children with pronounced characteristics (abilities or disabilities), this option is more acceptable for first-level schools.

Students in a class, brought together only on the basis of age, without taking into account their intellectual and individual abilities, cannot evenly and equally move forward in mastering knowledge. Students of the same class can spend from 5 minutes to an hour and a half to complete the same task. Some students have flexibility for this age, agility of thinking, the ability to generalize, and a creative approach to solving certain problems, while others begin to lag behind in completing the educational material. Such students lose interest in knowledge and develop a negative attitude towards learning. This leads to academic failure. The situation is no better with strong students who are forced to work less than their full potential due to the fact that the teacher teaches based on the "average" student. They gradually get used to the ease of completing educational tasks, and the first difficulties give rise to confusion and self-doubt.

And this leads to a decrease in academic performance. Therefore, the task of achieving the highest possible performance by each student can be solved only on the basis of studying the individual characteristics of students with a differentiated approach.

The purpose of a teacher's job is to educate every student. A differentiated approach to learning helps to achieve the goal, and the decisive role is played by the differentiation of tasks according to the degree of complexity and the degree of independence of students when performing exercises. This is especially important for weak students. The teacher's task is to bring them to the average level, so the work is organized in such a way that the degree of independence of students increases and the teacher's help decreases. Strong students need tasks of increased complexity that allow them to develop and realize the maximum potential of each person.

1. Theoretical basis for differentiated learning.
2. What is differentiation?
3. Differentiation translated from Latin “difference” means division, stratification of the whole into parts, forms, steps.
4. The educational process is considered differentiated, which is characterized by taking into account the typical individual differences of students.
5. The purpose of differentiated education: to organize the educational process based on taking into account the individual characteristics of the individual, i.e. at the level of his capabilities and abilities.
6. The goal of differentiated learning is to see the student’s individuality and preserve it, to help the child believe in himself, and to ensure his maximum development.

Stages of building differentiated learning.

- Studying the individual characteristics of students - physical (health), psychological, and personal.
- Identification of separate groups of students that differ in:
 - different levels of assimilation of the material at the moment;
 - level of performance and pace of work;
 - features of perception, memory, thinking;
 - balance of excitation and inhibition processes.
- Compilation or selection of differentiated tasks, including various techniques that help students cope with the task independently, or associated with increasing the volume and complexity of the task.
- Constant monitoring of the results of students’ work, in accordance with which the nature of differentiated tasks changes.

Children with learning disabilities are slow to learn material. They experience inertia in their thought processes and are constrained by the initially found methods of action. They experience noticeable difficulties whenever they have to switch from one operation to another.

Children with high learning ability are distinguished by high mobility of thought processes, a fast pace of progress, and a close connection between verbal, abstract and visual elements of thinking. The most favorable position is for a student who has rapidity and mobility of thought processes.

It is important for a teacher to know the characteristics of the mental activity of students in his class. It is necessary to find out how quickly and how deeply each student learns the material, whether they know how to defend their opinion, and what are the characteristics of their memory.

The psychological characteristics of students and different levels of their mental abilities naturally require differentiation of teaching.

Thus, the class is divided into three groups:

Group 1 – students with low learning abilities. This group of students requires a precise limitation of educational tasks, additional explanations of new things in the lesson, and constant monitoring by the teacher.

When working with weak students using a differentiated teaching method, there is no need for additional training after school. This solves the problem of children’s lack of free time.

The role of independent work for students in this group cannot be underestimated. If they are deprived of the opportunity to exercise on their own, they may become accustomed to acting only according to a model and only with outside help.

Group 2 – students with average abilities.

This group of students performs tasks of increased complexity, which are aimed not only at practicing educational material, but also at developing speech and logical thinking.

Group 3 – students with high academic abilities.

This group of students works with material of greater complexity, requiring the ability to apply knowledge in an unfamiliar situation and independently creatively approach solving educational problems.

Ways to differentiate educational activities.

I most often use a differentiated approach to students in lessons of consolidation and repetition of previously studied material.

Students do not need reinforcement and exercise at the same level or in the same amount. At this stage of work, stronger students have more time to complete additional tasks that expand and deepen their knowledge and skills. At the consolidation stage, I organize educational work so that each student does work that is feasible for himself, getting the opportunity to experience educational success in each lesson. Didactic support for a differentiated approach to students at the stage of consolidating the material is the selection of a system of exercises. This task system includes:

- a wide range of mandatory level tasks;
- task to prevent common mistakes;
- - tasks of increased complexity, intended for students who are quickly progressing in mastering the material.

Control and assessment are aimed not only, and this is very important, at identifying a certain result in knowledge and skills, but also, first of all, at the process of forming this knowledge in students to ensure targeted and timely correction. Monitoring and evaluation of a student's activity is considered only in dynamics relative to the child's previous successes and does not imply comparison with other children.

The main function of control is seen in constant monitoring of the progress of educational actions, timely detection of various errors in their implementation. The main principle of knowledge control is to minimize children's stress. The atmosphere in the classroom should be calm and friendly.

In my work, I use meaningful differentiation, in which I offer children tasks at different levels. The content of tasks may vary in level of creativity, level of difficulty, and volume.

The advantage of doing this is that I am able to distribute my attention more evenly between the students in each small group. While one group is working with the teacher, the others are completing the task independently.

Dividing the class into groups helps to organize mutual checking of each other's work and raises mutual responsibility for completing assignments, since a survey in the lesson is often also carried out in groups, and feasible individual tasks for each student, depending on his group, help the weak one feel that he is needed - he also does what he can. part of the overall work.

Thus, a differentiated approach to students in the learning process helps to prepare low-performing students to perceive new material, fill gaps in knowledge in a timely manner, make

wider use of the cognitive capabilities of students, especially strong ones, and constantly maintain interest in the subject.

I select tasks in such a way that, despite a single cognitive goal and general content, they differ in varying degrees of difficulty, that is, to achieve a single goal, students take different paths.

It is also important to note that I offer assignments for students to choose from. This allows them to assess their own capabilities in completing a task and contributes to the formation of such an important thing as predictive self-esteem.

It is possible to use not only substantive, but also organizational methods of differentiation. In this case, the content of the tasks is the same, and the work is differentiated according to the degree of independence of students or the level and nature of assistance to students.

Research by M. Djumaev has proven that the age of 6-9 years is a sensitive period in the development of thinking, the rapid development of which contributes to other cognitive processes [5]. and also pays attention to the fact that the learning process in primary school should be based on the thinking and imagination of younger schoolchildren [6]. School practice shows that the nature of learning knowledge and skills is individual for students. The same task may be difficult for some students, but not difficult for others. Some can highlight the main thing in objects and make comparisons, others only describe objects, while allowing for confusion of features.

The current stage of development of a comprehensive school requires the training of a teacher who is capable of implementing the principles of humanization of education, developmental education, and differentiation of the educational process. The focus of educational content on the quality of knowledge predetermines the search for approaches to learning that contribute not only to students' acquisition of knowledge, but also to personal development.

Any pedagogical technology affects the totality of content, forms, means, methods of organizing and implementing the educational process, aimed at solving the problems of training, education, and development of students. The new generation school requires primary school teachers to master teaching methods based on pedagogical technologies.

The formation of components of educational activity (motives, goals, actions, acceptance of the educational task by students, control and self-testing of the results of actions) determines changes in the student himself as a subject of learning. Younger students learn better when they use personal experience and study what suits their capabilities. How to make learning student-centered? Undoubtedly, the school is focused on the formation of personality traits desired by society.

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